

Digital Privacy Awareness on the Adoption of New Technologies in Ecommerce Platforms

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ABSTRACT

This paper looks at digital privacy, its aspects of trust, concerns and control, and its influence on the adoption of new technologies during and after the COVID-19 outbreak. It examines the current awareness of individuals of digital privacy and explores its effect on the relationship between digital privacy and the adoption of new technologies. The paper also investigates if the level of awareness of individuals has changed after COVID-19.

This research aims to bring renewed awareness to digital privacy changes and stimulate mindfulness of technological innovations and privacy concerns. The research will provide value for organisations that develop innovations, new products and new technologies in eCommerce, as it will provide insights into the importance of digital privacy for individuals in any future pandemic crisis era.

Keywords

eCommerce, Technology Adoption, Data Privacy, Data Sharing, User Security.

INTRODUCTION

Following the developments of the COVID-19 pandemic, which was a natural disruptor, users of digital applications became flushed with the growing number of user platforms and services enabled across any area of human social interaction. Visible areas relatable to everyone around were found in healthcare, business, security, social interaction, and eCommerce. For example, with the need to fulfil consumption demands, eCommerce became a digital playground; governments introduced monitoring apps to manage the spread of health incidents.

Technology-driven innovation platforms raised concerns about digital privacy because of the perceived and reported misuse of personal and sensitive data in social media and local news

channels.

The research is empirical and will use a quantitative method to measure and analyse the findings. A survey will be set up to investigate the level of attention platform users pay to their privacy when accepting and working with new technologies after a disruptive event like the COVID-19 crisis.

This research paper will lay its groundwork on two previously conducted studies and their associated theories. The first describes privacy and control using contact tracing apps like the CoronaMelder app. The second looks at the role of trust and privacy in e-retail services. Both papers examine the effect of privacy on the acceptance of new technologies.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

This research is based on the available literature that covers the relationship between digital privacy and its effect on purchasing power on eCommerce platforms. Digital Privacy refers to consumer privacy rights in e-services and the protection of an individual's information used or created using e-services (Rice & Sussan, 2016). Consumers' buying behaviour has increased during COVID-19 compared to the pre-pandemic period (Alzaidi & Agag, 2022). Purchasing power depends on trust and privacy concerns. Information quality, security concerns, ease of use, privacy and security assurance are the main drivers of trust and privacy concerns (Alzaidi & Agag, 2022).

Current literature has a gap in knowledge regarding the post-pandemic evaluation of the relationship between Digital Privacy and consumer behaviour on eCommerce platforms. Previous literature has not considered the moderating effect of Digital Privacy Awareness of individuals during the evaluation of the relationship. Digital Privacy Awareness is the level of knowledge of individuals about the importance of digital privacy, its technical implications on the service providers, and an understanding of how third parties can process

personal information and what harm it can bring to individuals.

This research will focus on filling the gaps. This will clarify the existing literature on the relationship between digital privacy and consumer behaviour while considering consumers' level of awareness. This clarification will help academia to have a more reliable picture of the current situation during the past-COVID era. This will also help businesses to have more context in understanding the problem and improve their product/service strategies going forward.

RESEARCH QUESTION

The research is focused on studying the three main components - digital privacy, accepting new technologies and individual awareness to privacy (also mentioned in this paper as attention level). It examines the theory behind the relationship between digital privacy and accepting new technologies.

In this document the term digital privacy is defined as the protection of the individual's data that is being used through digital channels. Such channels may collect, store and deliver this data to third parties for various purposes, which increases the risk of unauthorized access or even theft of personal and sensitive information. Individual's awareness in the scope of this text refers to the known perception of an individual of his own privacy state. Technology acceptance is the process of adaptation of users/individuals to certain new technology and their use. It is a complex process and a great challenge for keeping digital privacy at a high level. Different concerns may arise during the process of accepting new technologies. New technologies may refer to a wide variety of new trends for example AI, IoT, Cybersecurity, VR, datafication, etc. Technologies may vary from simple to more complex ideas and implementations, each facing a different perspective on digital privacy.

More specifically, the research examines the positive or negative influence of privacy as the independent variable on technological adoption as the dependent variable. Moreover, the research checks how the individual's awareness affects that relationship. The awareness, in this case, acts as a moderating variable. The research, therefore, aims to examine the above-mentioned relationships by answering the following main research question and sub-questions:

Main research question:

How significant has the attention level given to digital privacy within eCommerce platforms changed in connection to new technologies launched

Sub-questions:

1. How much influence does digital privacy have on usage of new eCommerce platforms/technologies?
 - a. Do digital privacy concerns (positively/negatively) influence the adoption of new technologies?
 - b. Does trust (in data exposure) positively/negatively influence the acceptance of new technologies?
2. How does individual awareness of digital privacy affect the acceptance of new technologies?
 - a. Does the attention level given to one's privacy (from pop-up cookies) affect user shopping behaviour?
 - b. What does awareness of digital privacy mean?

Conceptual Model and Theory

The first hypothesis refers to digital privacy & new technology acceptance. The research from Alzaidi & Agag (2022) studies trust and privacy concerns as the key drivers in accepting new technologies in the context of social media for e-retail services. The level of privacy concerns depends on the level of trust a customer has in a specific new technology."

Customer's willingness to use a system is positively influenced by their level of trust." Thus, we can conclude that having high trust/belief in a new technology and its dedicated purpose is influential and significantly impacts how the technology is adopted.

The study suggests that even if customers have a positive feeling about new technology, they might still be kept from adopting it due to concerns about their security and privacy. Next to that, another study from van Brakel et al. (2022) examines the adoption and use of contact tracing apps. It suggests that lack of trust and increased "feeling of surveillance", which is one aspect of privacy concerns, were the reasons for not downloading/adopting the new app.

Thus, we can hypothesize:

Hypothesis 1: Digital privacy concerns negatively influence the acceptance of new technologies.

The next two hypotheses refer to the individual's awareness of privacy / Attention level to privacy.

Hypothesis 2: An individual's awareness of privacy changes negatively while accepting new technologies

Hypothesis 3: The adoption of new technologies is positively influenced by the increased individual awareness of digital privacy.

Figure 1. Conceptual model

METHODOLOGY

This research paper will use a cross-sectional quantitative survey method to realise the study goals set out by this research team. In cross-sectional research, the survey questions will only be asked once to one set of respondents, and these respondents will not be followed up with further survey questions if the results change. The questions are structured in an informal way.

The main research question will be answered by gathering the data via a survey technique and analysis of the outcomes through regression testing. The sample population will try to diversify the category of respondents so that these include people that have used, or currently use at least one recognizable medium or channel for eCommerce activities. Channels for eCommerce activities recognized in this research survey includes apps and websites via digital mobile devices (such as phones, tablets), a personal computer (laptop or desktop), or a self-ordering kiosk (such as found at KFC, Burger King, etc..).

The objective is to trigger a respondent's recollection of events or instances where that person has given personal data / information in exchange for accepting cookies

The sampling frame consists of the people in the close network of authors (convenience sampling, thus, it will follow non-probability sampling. The total size of the sampling frame is 100 people. Respondents within the sampling frame are expected to have a diverse demographic: mainly residents of the Netherlands, wide age ranges and occupations.

The survey is enabled through self-administered electronic mode and is distributed via emails, and Google Forms are used to collect the responses. The questions within the survey are split into four categories:

- i. The first category aims to record the demographic information of respondents.
- ii. The second category aims to rank the knowledge of respondents of digital privacy.
- iii. The third category aims to rank the awareness levels of individuals related to digital privacy.
- iv. The fourth category aims to collect data about the number of / level of technology acceptance.

The following table contains some likely questions to be included as part of the survey:

RESULT

In this research paper, the team expects to send the survey to a mini sample size of about 10 people and expects at least an 80% response rate. The goal is to see if any relationships or knowledge can be gained from the distinct demographics of the respondents. Such as respondent categories (e.g., students, academia, non-formal working groups, professional working groups, etc.).

The team expects that a comparison in line with the hypothesis will give insights into respondents' awareness levels towards digital privacy. Results from the survey questions will provide the scope for the discussions/conclusions and the recommendations that our paper will provide.

The survey data has been extracted through Google forms in the form of a .csv file. The .csv file has been loaded into SPSS to run the statistical regression analysis. Before the regression analysis can be run, the data first need to be accommodated. For this purpose, three new variables have been computed – namely (i) privacy, (ii) awareness, and (iii)ANT (stands for “accepting new technologies”). The variables have been computed by finding the median of the respected survey data variables that caught the results. Finally, the analysis has been performed using the ANT as the dependent variable and privacy and awareness variables as independent variables. Even though awareness in our case acts as a moderating variable, for ease of the analysis it is treated as independent. The demographic variables have been left out.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Looking at the results of the regression analysis, we can see that the standard coefficients of privacy and individual awareness are negative. This makes us think that there is a negative correlation between these variables and the accepting new technologies variable. However, looking more into the significance level of these parameters, we see p-values of 0.715 and 0.362, which are extremely

high values (>0.05). From this, we cannot conclude that privacy and awareness affect accepting new technologies.

cue” (Frik A., Mittone, L. (2019). In many cases, this can be based on historical interactions with the same platform, or familiarity with generic terminology associated with business language.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.226	1.332		3.172	.011
	Awareness	-.150	.397	-.120	-.377	.715
	Privacy	-.220	.229	-.305	-.961	.362

a. Dependent Variable: ANT

Figure 2: SPSS Regression Analysis

The SPSS results are not as expected. This can be caused by several factors. One would be that the sample size used for the analysis is relatively small – only 14 respondents were recorded for the survey and analyzed as represented above.

Another possible cause would be the small number of questions per group that have been asked to the respondents as well as the accuracy of the questions.

Hence, to increase the reliability of the research, we suggest using a bigger sample, improving the quality and accuracy of the questions, as well as including more questions per group.

Behaviour-based decisioning

Consumers initially engage in e-commerce with the primary goal of purchasing a product or service, not of protecting their personal information. (Frik & Mittone (2017). The results show us that users will primarily focus on the shopping goals and benefits from an eCommerce platform to fulfill a need while paying little attention to the privacy concerns, paying more attention to the features and characteristics of the technology.

This is in contrast to the business entity where this privacy information is in very lengthy texts, hidden behind inconspicuous links. Often times, these are written in complex terminology that are not easy to interpret when a platform user (shopper) is in a hurry. The respondents also give the insight that the primary goal of visiting an eCommerce platform is not for digital privacy reasons but seeking to meet a demand delivering value creation. This can be seen in the results indicating if the T&Cs are read prior to accepting cookies. User behaviour indicates that in situations where the user is not certain about the content, meaning and processing of their cookie-related data, that people “tend to rely on contextual

Trust-based decisioning

The results also portray a lack of trust in the composition and usage of cookies and its invasion on digital privacy. Trust is a much needed currency in the adoption of new technologies, especially more in eCommerce platforms. While users have a specific need to fulfil on these platforms, and may appreciate a good offer, there is very little likelihood that users want their digital footprints used against them for future promotions or at the hands of unintended third parties.

As with all new technologies, usage data, location history and other metrics during each visit means that every website or digital platform logs every action of users. Generic everyday interaction of these platforms by everyone, from buying basic necessities to luxury items exposes users to vulnerabilities online. the survey results shows that users may indicate significantly distrust of an eCommerce platform, but not necessarily stop using the platform. Hence, there is an inherent fear of data loss numbed by personal gratification derived from the purchase of an item via a digital platform. This can be seen by responses which also indicate that users may exhibit a certain comfort level when providing their personal data if they have assurance that it will not be misused.

With this survey, the questions are asked independently such that respondent do not have to let one judgement override the other, yet it could be that when making decisions in real life, there is a very thin line between the way users think about these scenarios and multiple factors that influence their interactions on eCommerce platforms. Thus, it cannot be ruled out that emotional sentiments and excitement may have an impact when a user is in the “shopping moment”. This can be seen in the results where users may likely accept non-mandatory cookies and third-party cookie data during a digital platform interaction.

Other limitations

Other factors such as age, geographical location and educational level may have an impact on the level and type of awareness a user has on digital privacy awareness. Thus, for this survey it is already indicated that there may be some likelihood of limitations – some instances are the survey size

sample, the geographic region(s) of the respondents and the laws governing digital privacy of their data on digital platforms. The responses were also based on what was reported by the respondents based on personal opinions. Whether these provide empirical insights or not would depend on how much factors were taken into account when making the decisions in the survey.

It could be that in a full research, laboratory or field experiments may provide a better validity and reliability of the results. The datasets derived also may not necessarily tell the full story with a larger sample size. The research team took care to ensure that the questions were the same for all respondents, not manipulated or randomized and there was no bias in the composition of the questions or in the selection of respondents.

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APPENDIX

The following table contains some likely questions to be included as part of the survey:

<i>Category</i>	<i>Question</i>	<i>Type</i>
<i>Demographics</i>	Age Group	Single choice question 18-24 25-34 35-44 45-54 55+
	Education	Single choice question High school diploma College Bachelor's Degree Master's Degree PhD degree
<i>Digital Privacy Knowledge</i>	Gender	Single choice question Male Female
	How familiar are you with the term Digital Privacy?	Likert Scale (1-7) - Least familiar – Most familiar
<i>Individual's awareness</i>	How often do you read the Terms of Services before accepting cookies?	Scale (1-5) - Never - Always
	How safe do you feel when accepting new cookies?	Likert Scale (1-7) - Least safe – Most safe
<i>Technology Adoption</i>	How comfortable do you feel with providing personal data on eCommerce sites if you think they will not be misused?	Likert Scale (1-7) - Least comfortable – Most comfortable
	How likely are you rejecting to use a website if you see "shady" the Terms of Services on a website?	Likert Scale (1-7) - Never reject – Always reject
	How likely are you to accept non-mandatory cookies and third-party cookie data on eCommerce sites when shopping	Likert Scale (1-7) - Least likely – Most likely
	How often do you review all cookies policies before proceeding to the main eCommerce sites?	Scale (1-5) - Never – Always
	How satisfied are you with the intrusion of cookie data on your online shopping experience?	Likert Scale (1-7) – least satisfied – highly satisfied

Table 1: Sample survey questions and response type